

A Note on Differential Geometry of the Curves in E^4

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Abstract: In this note, we prove that every regular curve in four dimensional Euclidean space satisfies a vector differential equation of fifth order. Thereafter, in the same space, a relation among curvatures functions of inclined curves is obtained in terms of harmonic curvatures, which is related with Smarandache geometries ([5]).

Key Words: Euclidean space, Frenet formulas, inclined curves, harmonic curvatures.

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§1. Introduction

At the beginning of the twentieth century, A.Einstein's theory opened a door of use of new geometries. These geometries mostly have higher dimensions. In higher dimensional Euclidean space, researchers treated some topics of classical differential geometry [1], [2] and [3].

It is well-known that, if a curve differentiable in an open interval, at each point, a set of mutually orthogonal unit vectors can be constructed. And these vectors are called *Frenet frame* or *moving frame vectors*. The rates of these frame vectors along the curve define curvatures of the curves. The set, whose elements are frame vectors and curvatures of a curve, is called *Frenet apparatus of the curves*.

In [1], author wrote a relation of inclined curves. In this work, first, we prove that every regular curve in four dimensional Euclidean space satisfies a vector differential equation of fifth order. This result is obtained by means of Frenet formulas. Then using relation of inclined curves written in [1], we express a new relation for inclined curves in Euclidean space E^4 , which is related with Smarandache geometries, see [5] for details.

§2. Preliminaries

To meet the requirements in the next sections, here, the basic elements of the theory of curves in the space E^4 are briefly presented (a more complete elementary treatment can be found in [4]).

Let $\alpha : I \subset \mathbb{R} \rightarrow E^4$ be an arbitrary curve in the Euclidean space E^4 . Recall that the curve α is said to be of unit speed (or parameterized by arclength function s) if $\langle \alpha'(s), \alpha'(s) \rangle = 1$, where $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ is the standard scalar (inner) product of E^4 given by

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$$\langle X, Y \rangle = x_1y_1 + x_2y_2 + x_3y_3 + x_4y_4, \quad (1)$$

for each $X = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4)$, $Y = (y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4) \in E^4$. In particular, the norm of a vector $X \in E^4$ is given by

$$\|X\| = \sqrt{\langle X, X \rangle}.$$

Let $\{T(s), N(s), B(s), E(s)\}$ be the moving frame along the unit speed curve α . Then the Frenet formulas are given by [2]

$$\begin{bmatrix} T' \\ N' \\ B' \\ E' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \kappa & 0 & 0 \\ -\kappa & 0 & \tau & 0 \\ 0 & -\tau & 0 & \sigma \\ 0 & 0 & -\sigma & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} T \\ N \\ B \\ E \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

Here T, N, B and E are called the *tangent*, the *normal*, the *binormal* and the *trinormal vector fields of the curves*, respectively, and the functions $\kappa(s), \tau(s)$ and $\sigma(s)$ are called the first, the second and the third curvature of a curve in E^4 , respectively. Also, the functions $H_1 = \frac{\kappa}{\tau}$ and $H_2 = \frac{H_1'}{\sigma}$ are called *harmonic curvatures* of the curves in E^4 , where $\kappa \neq 0, \tau \neq 0$ and $\sigma \neq 0$. Let $\alpha : I \subset \mathbb{R} \rightarrow E^4$ be a regular curve. If tangent vector field T of α forms a constant angle with unit vector U , this curve is called an inclined curve in E^4 .

In the same space, the author wrote a characterization for inclined curves with the following theorem in [1].

Theorem 2.1 *Let $\alpha : I \subset \mathbb{R} \rightarrow E^4$ be an unit speed regular curve with curvatures $\kappa \neq 0, \tau \neq 0$ and $\sigma \neq 0$. α is an inclined curve if and only if there is a relation*

$$\frac{\kappa}{\tau} = A \cos \int_0^s \sigma ds + B \sin \int_0^s \sigma ds, \quad (3)$$

where $A, B \in \mathbb{R}$.

§3. Vector Differential Equation of Fifth Order Satisfied by Regular Curves in E^4

Theorem 3.1 *Let $X : I \subset \mathbb{R} \rightarrow E^4$ be an unit speed regular curve with curvatures $\kappa \neq 0, \tau \neq 0$ and $\sigma \neq 0$ in E^4 . Position vector and curvatures of α satisfies a vector differential equation of fifth order.*

Proof Let $X : I \subset \mathbb{R} \rightarrow E^4$ be an unit speed regular curve with curvatures $\kappa \neq 0, \tau \neq 0$ and $\sigma \neq 0$ in E^4 . Considering Frenet equations, we write that

$$N = \frac{T'}{\kappa} \quad (4)$$

and

$$B = \frac{1}{\tau}(\kappa T + N'). \quad (5)$$

Substituting (3) in (1)₃, we get

$$B' = -\frac{\tau}{\kappa}T' + \sigma E. \quad (6)$$

Then, differentiating (3) and substituting it to (4), we find

$$B = \frac{1}{\tau} \left[\kappa T + \left(\frac{T'}{\kappa} \right)' \right]. \quad (7)$$

Taking the integral on both sides of (1)₄, we know

$$E = - \int \sigma B ds \quad (8)$$

and substituting (6) to (7), we get

$$E = - \int \frac{\sigma}{\tau} \left[\kappa T + \left(\frac{T'}{\kappa} \right)' \right] ds. \quad (9)$$

Applying (8) in (5), we have

$$B' = -\frac{\tau}{\kappa}T' - \sigma \int \frac{\sigma}{\tau} \left[\kappa T + \left(\frac{T'}{\kappa} \right)' \right] ds. \quad (10)$$

Similarly, differentiating (6) and considering (9), then

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left(\frac{1}{\tau} \right)' \left[\frac{T''\kappa - T'\kappa'}{\kappa^2} + \kappa T \right] + \\ \frac{1}{\tau} \left[\frac{(T'''\kappa + T'\kappa'')\kappa^2 - 2\kappa\kappa'(T''\kappa - T'\kappa')}{\kappa^3} + \kappa'T + \kappa T' \right] \\ + \frac{\tau}{\kappa}T' + \sigma \int \frac{\sigma}{\tau} \left[\kappa T + \left(\frac{T'}{\kappa} \right)' \right] ds \end{array} \right\} = 0 \quad (11)$$

is obtained. One more differentiating of (10) and simplifying this with $\dot{X} = T$, $\ddot{X} = T'$, $\ddot{\dot{X}} = T''$, $X^{(IV)} = T'''$ and $X^{(V)} = T^{(IV)}$, we know

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left[\frac{1}{\kappa\tau} \right] X^{(V)} + \left[\frac{\kappa'}{\kappa^2\tau} + \left(\frac{1}{\tau} \right)' \frac{1}{\kappa} + \left(\frac{1}{\kappa^4\tau} \right)' \kappa + \frac{2}{\kappa^3\tau} \right] \cdot X^{(IV)} + \\ \left[\left(\frac{1}{\tau} \right)'' \frac{1}{\kappa} - 2 \left(\frac{1}{\tau} \right)' \frac{\kappa'}{\kappa^2} - \kappa^2 \kappa' \tau \left(\frac{1}{\kappa^4\tau} \right)' - \frac{\kappa''}{\kappa^2\tau} - \frac{2}{\kappa^3\tau} \kappa'^2 + \kappa^5 + \frac{\tau}{\kappa} + \frac{\sigma^2}{\kappa\tau} \right] \cdot \ddot{\dot{X}} \\ \left[-\frac{\kappa'}{\kappa^2} \left(\frac{1}{\tau} \right)'' - \frac{\kappa''}{\kappa^2} \left(\frac{1}{\tau} \right)' + \frac{2\kappa'^2}{\kappa^3} \left(\frac{1}{\tau} \right)' + \kappa \left(\frac{1}{\tau} \right)' + 2\kappa'^2 \kappa \left(\frac{1}{\kappa^4\tau} \right) + \kappa^5 \left(\frac{1}{\kappa^4\tau} \right)' \right] \cdot \ddot{\dot{X}} \\ - \frac{2\kappa'\kappa''}{\kappa^3\tau} + \frac{\kappa'\sigma}{\tau} + \left(\frac{\tau}{\kappa} \right)' + \frac{\sigma^2}{\kappa\tau} - \kappa^2 \kappa'' \left(\frac{1}{\kappa^4\tau} \right)' - \frac{\sigma^2 \kappa'}{\kappa\tau} \\ \left[\kappa \left(\frac{1}{\tau} \right)'' + \kappa' \left(\frac{1}{\tau} \right)'' + \kappa' \left(\frac{1}{\tau} \right)' + \kappa^4 \kappa' \left(\frac{1}{\kappa^4\tau} \right)' + \frac{4\kappa'^2}{\kappa\tau} + \frac{\kappa''}{\tau} + \frac{\sigma^2 \kappa'}{\tau} \right] \cdot \dot{X} \end{array} \right\} = 0. \quad (12)$$

The formula (12) proves the theorem as desired. \square

§4. A Characterization of Inclined Curves in E^4

Theorem 4.1 Let $\alpha : I \subset R \rightarrow E^4$ be an unit speed regular curve with curvatures $\kappa \neq 0, \tau \neq 0$ and $\sigma \neq 0$ in E^4 . α is an inclined curve if and only if

$$H_1^2 + H_2^2 = \text{constant}, \quad (13)$$

where H_1 and H_2 are harmonic curvatures.

Proof Let α be an regular inclined curve in E^4 . In this case, we can write

$$\frac{\kappa}{\tau} = A. \cos \int_0^s \sigma ds. + B. \sin \int_0^s \sigma ds, \quad (14)$$

where $A, B \in R$. If we differentiate (14) respect to s , we get

$$\frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{d}{ds} \left(\frac{\kappa}{\tau} \right) = -A. \sin \int_0^s \sigma ds. + B. \cos \int_0^s \sigma ds. \quad (15)$$

Similarly, one more differentiating (15) respect to s , we have

$$\frac{d}{ds} \left[\frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{d}{ds} \left(\frac{\kappa}{\tau} \right) \right] = -A\sigma \sin \int_0^s \sigma ds. - B\sigma \cos \int_0^s \sigma ds. \quad (16)$$

Using notations $\sigma H_1 = \sigma \frac{\kappa}{\tau}$ and $\frac{dH_2}{ds}$ in (16), we find

$$\sigma H_1 + \frac{dH_2}{ds} = 0. \quad (17)$$

Multiplying both sides of (17) with $\frac{1}{\sigma} H_1' = H_2$, we obtain

$$H_1 H_1' + H_2 H_2' = 0. \quad (18)$$

The formula (18) yields that

$$H_1^2 + H_2^2 = \text{constant}. \quad (19)$$

Conversely, let relation (19) hold. Differentiating (19) respect to s , we know

$$H_1 H_1' + H_2 H_2' = 0. \quad (20)$$

Similarly differentiating of expressions of harmonic curvatures and using these in (20), we have the following differential equation

$$\frac{1}{\sigma^2} H_1'' + \frac{1}{\sigma} \left(\frac{1}{\sigma} \right)' H_1' + H_1 = 0. \quad (21)$$

Using an exchange variable $t = \int_0^s \sigma ds$ in (20),

$$\ddot{H}_1 + H_1 = 0. \quad (22)$$

Here, the notation \ddot{H}_1 indicates derivative of H_1 according to t . Solution of (22) follows that

$$H_1 = A \cos t + B \sin t, \quad (23)$$

where $A, B \in \mathbb{R}$. Therefore, we write that

$$\frac{\kappa}{\tau} = A \cdot \cos \int_0^s \sigma ds + B \cdot \sin \int_0^s \sigma ds. \quad (24)$$

By Theorem 2.1, (24) implies that α is an inclined curve in E^4 .

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